

Parallel field programmable gate array implementation of the sum of absolute differences algorithm used in the stereoscopic system

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ABSTRACT

Stereo vision is a popular method for an artificial vision-based environment perception system used in various applications such as intelligent transportation. With two cameras, the disparity map is calculated to find the distance and depth of objects in front of a moving vehicle. The key element of the stereoscopic system is based on the sum of absolute differences (SAD) algorithm, which is the most repeated operation in the stereo matching subsystem; however, this algorithm requires a very intensive processing time, statistical analysis show that the SAD block can consume more than 80% of the overall processing time of the algorithm. In this paper we propose a highly efficient hardware architecture of the SAD algorithm for real time stereo matching, the proposed architecture is established by a hierarchical parallel architecture of the SAD block, and verified by simulation and successfully implemented in Cyclone IV field programmable gate array (FPGA), it provides a significant reduction of processing time and the performance of the stereo imaging system is able to achieve 30 frames per second of 640×480 resolution color images.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Stereo vision is an imaging technique similar to the vision principle way of the human eyes. It involves using two cameras to generate a three dimensional image. The depth map can be generated by comparing the offset of homologous pixels from the two cameras. This depth map is a three dimensional representation of the real world. These systems are becoming more and more essential for several applications, such as mobile robot navigation, intelligent transportation. Intelligent vehicles and mobile robots can use stereo vision to improve the perception of the environment and consequently the performance of object detection, which is one of the challenges of these applications.

The main idea of stereo vision systems is the estimation of the image depth obtained from a disparity map through stereo matching. The core of the stereo vision system is mainly composed of a computational block that compares the two images to find the objects that match and estimate the distance between the objects and the cameras. This comparison technique is based on several algorithms, such as the sum of absolute differences (SAD) and sum of square differences (SSD) algorithms [1] that find the homologous pixels.

The SAD algorithm measures the similarity between image blocks by taking the absolute difference of each pixel in the right image block and the corresponding pixel in the left image block. These differences are summed to create a simple measure of block similarity. This algorithm is based on three general approaches to computing the disparity map: local, global, and semi global algorithms as presented in the works [2]–[4]. Local algorithms try to find optimal disparities for small image regions with fixed windows using local differences; however, global algorithms apply a large computational time based on global cost optimization. Finally, the semi global algorithm incorporates the advantages of both local and global algorithms by achieving relatively low complexity. The analysis results of previous works on the complexity of these three approaches show that the local algorithms present a good compromise between the computational complexity and the real time processing constraints.

In order to ensure the compromise between a higher computational complexity of the SAD algorithm and an accelerated processing time of the stereo vision system on embedded platforms, different optimization approaches have been performed in recent years. Many research works has been devoted to the implementation of the SAD algorithm using software and hardware approaches to achieve real time processing for the stereo vision systems. Most of the software implementations use the graphics processing units (GPU) processor which presents an efficient environment to implement the parallel processing of the SAD algorithm. For example, Lu *et al.* [4] propose a dynamic window algorithm implementation with GPU processor that achieves a speed of 17 fps. In another GPU processor based implementation, Gong *et al.* [5] propose a software implementation of the SAD algorithm based on the GPU processor, the result shows a processing performance of 10 fps. In Wang *et al.* [6] a multiple obstacle detection and tracking system using stereo vision is developed to avoid collision in reel time. Other works [3], [7] present an implementation in real time of the stereo vision system based on the GPU processor. Another way to optimize the processing time of the SAD algorithm is to use a software implementation based on the digital signal processing (DSP) and acorn risc machine (ARM) processor. Lin and Chiu [8], propose a new approach to implement the stereo vision system based on the SAD algorithm and uses the DSP processor to speed up the difference sum calculation. Another software implementation based on the ARM processor with software parallelism of the SAD algorithm has been proposed in Sejai *et al.* [9].

However, due to the high computational complexity of the SAD algorithm, a hardware implementation on a reconfigurable circuit is required. Many hardware implementations have been proposed in the literature. A hardware implementation of the SAD algorithm on field programmable gate array (FPGA) components can accelerate the processing time of the stereo vision system by exploiting the most developed resources of FPGAs. Wang *et al.* [10] implemented a real time high quality stereo vision system in FPGA by using absolute difference census cost initialization, cross based cost aggregation, and semi global optimization, the system provides high quality depth results for high definition images. Seo *et al.* [11], propose a new hardware architecture for the implementation of the stereo vision system that reuses the intermediate results to minimize the processing time and memory access. Zha *et al.* [12] propose an improved global stereo matching algorithm that is implemented on a single FPGA for real time applications. The proposed system is a fully pipelined stereo vision system that provides a dense disparity image with real time. Kalomiros and Lygouras [13], [14] propose a system with two stereo accelerators implemented using reconfigurable hardware, the SAD algorithm and a dynamic programming technique is compared. Georgoulas and Andreadis [15] present the parallel pipelined design and hardware implementation of a fuzzy inference system based real time stereo vision system. Gardel *et al.* [16], the SAD and SSD algorithms implemented in an FPGA were used to obtain a disparity map. On the other hand, Ferreira *et al.* [17] use a technique of background subtraction to detect the target object and create segmented images. Murphy *et al.* [18] use the census transform to calculate the disparity. In a more recent work from Manjunatha *et al.* [19] propose an FPGA implementation of the SAD algorithm for video applications. In Koshta *et al.* [20], absolute difference circuit implementation on FPGA is proposed to increase speed performance and to minimize the occupied resources on FPGA for SAD calculation. QianYu and Yi [21] a hardware platform based on FPGA is built of a target detection and tracking system, after analyzing SAD algorithm and cross search algorithm, this paper focuses on the design of parallel search structure of tracking module, parallel matching structure of search module and parallel computing structure of SAD unit.

Based on a deep analysis of subsequent work on the stereo vision system, the calculation of disparity is complex and obtained using census transformation, SAD, SSD, or dynamic programming techniques. The mathematical operations must be performed efficiently to be used in real time stereo vision systems. Therefore, our work proposes to use a simple and fast architecture for disparity calculation, which is based on a SAD algorithm. In this paper, we present an optimized architecture of the SAD algorithm implemented in a reconfigurable FPGA. This architecture is based on parallelism processing to accelerate the computation time in order to respect the processing time constraints of a stereo vision system. The system uses two image inputs (left and right) with a video graphics array (VGA) resolution (640×480 pixels), it is generic in terms of window size and disparity range.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 gives an overview of the techniques available in the literature for the stereo vision system. The design methodology and the architecture developed of the SAD algorithm are presented in section 3. Section 4 describes the details of hardware implementation. Finally, section 5 concludes the work.

2. OVERVIEW OF STEREO VISION SYSTEM

2.1. Stereo vision algorithm

The concept of stereo vision algorithms use binocular vision to reconstruct the lost third dimension in the images, this technique uses two images of the same scene taken from different view points. The geometry of stereo vision system for a parallel camera configuration is based on epipolar geometry [2], which considerably limits the search area by reducing it to a single horizontal dimension. The depth perception by stereo vision is mainly provided by the matching computation method to find the homologous pixels between the two images. This depth perception is based on the square intensity differences (SD) or absolute intensity differences (AD), which are the most common methods as described Scharstein *et al.* [2].

The binocular stereo vision system consists of two left and right cameras of the same specification [22], the cameras remain on the same plane, which ensures that the horizontal axes of the left and right cameras system are on the same line and parallel to the imaging plane [23]. The (1) is used to calculate the distance D between the object P and the two cameras, in which (x_L, x_R) represent the coordinates of the corresponding pixel in the left and right image, and d is the point P disparity.

$$d = x_R - x_L \quad (1)$$

The relationship between the distance and the disparity is represented by (2). The distance between the cameras and an object is inversely proportional to the disparity. The disparity map contains the disparity of each pixel of the original image, and it is calculated by the stereo vision algorithms and used with the triangulation for the calculation of the distance to the object. B is the baseline of the stereo camera and F is the focal length of the camera.

$$D = \frac{B \times F}{d} \quad (2)$$

The stereo vision algorithm uses a block of correspondence which is the matching pixels process of the left and right image that correspond to the same point P projection in real world. A pixel's block, surrounding the pixel under consideration, is used for the matching. This pixels group is called the matching window and increases the accuracy of the match because a window provides more accurate description of an object instead of a single individual pixel. A matching window in the left image is matched with similar windows in the right image using SAD block matching; the matching windows number is limited by the size of the disparity range. The matching window in the right image is determined and the difference between their horizontal coordinates of the center pixel is considered as the disparity value for that pixel. Similarly, the disparity map is created by calculating the disparity for each pixel in the image as illustrate in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The stereo matching algorithm

2.2. SAD block matching algorithm

SAD is a pixel based matching method [24]. Stereo vision system uses the SAD algorithm to compare a pixels window in one image with a pixels window in second image to find the corresponding pixels. The SAD algorithm calculates the absolute difference between each pair of matching pixels and sums all these values to find the SAD valueas shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Global view of one SAD block

A SAD value does not give any information about the two corresponding pixels. Many SAD values will be calculated from different windows for the reference window, the SAD value with the smallest value of all the SAD values is the best matching pixel. Many methods have been defined to calculate the disparity d , between the candidate and reference images such as the work Lazaros *et al.* [25], which proposes to use $n \times n$ window to scan the image, and they are three main methods available to perform the calculation [26]. The first method is based on the SSD algorithm, which is given by (3).

$$SSD(x, y, d) = \sum_{(x,y) \in w} (I_L(x, y) - I_R(x, y - d))^2 \quad (3)$$

The normalized cross correlation (NCC) algorithm is the second method to determine the correspondence between two windows around a pixel of interest. It is more accurate and less sensitive to proportional changes in intensity, but it has a very expensive computational complexity. In (4) expresses the formula of the NCC technique.

$$NCC(x, y, d) = \frac{\sum_{(x,y) \in w} I_L(x, y) \cdot I_R(x, y - d)}{\sqrt{\sum_{(x,y) \in w} I_L^2(x, y) \cdot \sum_{(x,y) \in w} I_R^2(x, y - d)}} \quad (4)$$

The last method is the SAD algorithm and its calculation formula is mentioned in (5), it considers the absolute difference between the intensity of each pixel in the reference block and the corresponding pixel in the target block. (x, y) is the location of each pixel, I_L and I_R is the intensity of left and right image pixel. The minimum value of the disparity range SAD gives us the location of the best match for the template in the source image, however the disparity d can be calculated by (6).

$$SAD(x, y, d) = \sum_{(x,y) \in w} |I_L(x, y) - I_R(x, y - d)| \quad (5)$$

$$d = \min(SADs) \quad (6)$$

The disparity map is obtained after several iterations through each pixel of the left image, the sum of absolute values is calculated for the entire window with the pixel under consideration at the center. The window of the right image is then shifted by one pixel to the left and the SAD value is calculated again. This operation is repeated until all number of disparities (disparity range) has been analyzed. The resulting disparity value is obtained for the disparity level that generated the minimum SAD value.

The SAD algorithm has been used in many research studies. Based on simple calculations, this algorithm is an appropriate method for a hardware implementation, as SSD has a higher computational complexity compared to SAD, because it involves many multiplication operations. NCC is even more complex to both SAD and SSD, because it involves many multiplication, division and square root operations [26]. The SAD method [27] is the most widely used matching technique in stereo vision algorithms, due to its low computational complexity, excellent performance and ease of hardware implementation.

3. PROPOSED HARDWARE ARCHITECTURE

For a real time implementation of a stereo vision system, a hardware architecture of the SAD algorithm is proposed to achieve the best performance. This proposed architecture uses two separate buffers to store the input data of the left and right images with 640×480 resolution to reduce memory access. The window buffers store the different lines of the left and right image respectively, and contain the data needed to calculate the (i, j) point, this window buffer is generic, we can use $n \times n$ as the window size. The hardware design explores parallel data processing to achieve real time processing constraints. Figure 3 shows the top level of the proposed hardware architecture of the SAD algorithm.

Figure 3. Hardware block diagram of the proposed architecture

The main challenge met by this architecture is based on the proposal of the original and parallel SAD block, this SAD computation block requires only two basic operations, addition and subtraction. The SAD algorithm is the simplest metric that considers all the pixels of the block for calculation and also separately, which makes its implementation simpler and parallel. As a result, the SAD block is mainly composed of abs/sub blocks, an adders and a multiplexer that indicates the disparity d . The multiplexer compares two input SAD values, it outputs the minimum SAD value used in the comparison in the next step. The left image window and all the right image windows from (i, j) to $(i, j + \text{disparity range})$ are sent to the SAD block which simultaneously computes the SAD value which is based on the parallelism processing to speed up the computation time of our system, and all these blocks are controlled and synchronized by a finite state machine as shown in the Figure 4.

The SAD between two windows of size 3×3 centered on (i, j) of the left image and on $(i, j + \text{disparity range } 20)$ of the right image, the 9 absolute difference pixels are calculated in parallel and then summed to generate the final disparity value. For each clock cycle, the right window moves to the right, moving a new window column. This continues until the maximum disparity is reached, the minimum disparity of differences is determined. At this point, the left window moves one window column, while the right window is reloaded. We write the disparity d (horizontal distance) to the corresponding pixel in the disparity map for each block. Figure 5 shows how we can implement the different steps of the SAD block calculation.

As shown in Figure 6, the proposed SAD architecture is composed of three absolute difference blocks, two adders, and a multiplexer. The absolute difference block calculates the sum of three absolute differences of two input data with three pixels. The multiplexer compares two inputs SAD values and generates the minimum SAD value used in the comparison in the next step.

The window size of the SAD algorithm used to calculate disparity is 3×3 pixels; with a maximum disparity range of our design is 0 to 19 pixels. The image rows are read from the left and right images into buffers. This is done to speed up the access to the pixels from the next SAD window, because the external memory access is very slow compared to the memory located in the FPGA board. The three output rows of the image buffer is shifted into windows buffer to allow access to 20 values at the same time to compute the minimum SAD value for 20 SAD windows, and to calculate the disparity d between the homologous pixels. From that moment, for each clock cycle the right window buffer will shift to the right, moving a new window column, instead of re-reading the whole window from the image buffer. This operation continues until the maximum disparity has been reached. At this point the left window buffer shifts one window position, while the right window buffer is started the calculation of SAD values from this second column position.

Figure 4. Finite state machine diagram

Figure 5. SAD block calculation

Figure 6. SAD proposed architecture

4. EXPERIMENT RESULTS

The proposed SAD architecture is developed in very high speed integrated circuits hardware description language (VHDL) and synthesised using altera Cyclone IV FPGA. Figure 7 shows experimental steps for implementation of the proposed reconfigurable SAD system. For verifying the output data of the stereoscopic system, various images of stereo matching design are tested based on the middlebury dataset.

Figure 7. Block diagram of the global system

The both right and left images are converted to a grayscale images and stocked in the external synchronous dynamic random-access memory (SDRAM) memory on the FPGA platform. Triangulation method is used to determinate the distance between the object and the stereo system. The disparity map is displayed on the VGA monitor with the depth of the different objects. The implementation was done on altera Cyclone IV FPGA. Figure 8 show the schematic view of the synthesis result.

The results of the hardware implementation confirm that the proposed system can accurately generate depth maps by using left and right images. Table 1 gives the complete devices usages summary. We can see that our design spent 576 logic elements and use only 49152 bits of internal memory. There is one SAD block that can process three image lines in parallel. However the performance of the algorithm can be improved with more SAD parallel blocks.

To evaluate the proposed hardware implementation of proposed SAD architecture in terms of the device, window size, disparity range, algorithm, frame size used by similar works. The comparison results show that the proposed architecture had good performance, and exhibited higher computational efficiency compared to the other works. In addition, the parallel operations architecture effectively reduced the computation time of the proposed architecture. Processing two stereo images with the 640×480 resolution and for a 500 Mhz FPGA frequency gives us approximately 16×10^6 clock cycles.

To solve the problem of the extensive processing time generated by the full search based block matching of the SAD algorithm, a parallel hardware architecture of the SAD algorithm is proposed.

As mentioned above, this proposed parallel hardware architecture reduces the processing time of the full search algorithm and meet the reel time requirements. Experimentally, The proposed stereo vision system show that our FPGA implementation of the system is very efficient in terms of computational speed up and can operates in a real time with 30 frame per second (FPS) compared to the similar works as presented in the Table 2. On the other hand, notice that the use of FPGA resources presented in Table 1 make the system very flexible and it can be seen that the number of occupied resources on FPGA is reduced in the proposed SAD architecture than the works referenced in [28], [29], allowing the designers to implement other algorithms.

Figure 8. The RTL schematic view of the proposed architecture

Table 1. Resources required for implementing the proposed architecture on the Cyclone IV FPGA device

Resources	Used / available / (% of total used)
Total logic elements	576 / 21280 (3%)
Total combinational functions	572 / 21280 (3%)
Dedicated logic registers	367 / 21280 (2%)
Total pins	60 / 167 (36%)
Total memory bits	49152 / 774144 (6%)

Table 2. Comparison with other works

Reference	Device	FPS	Window size	Disparity range	Algorithm	Frame size
[30]	Altera Cyclone II	30	3×3	32	SAD	640×480
[31]	Altera Cyclone III	30	5×5	64	SAD	1396×1110
[32]	Altera Stratix IV	46 / 400	25×25	256 / 128	SAD	1280×1024/640×480
[33]	Xilinx Virtex XCV-2000E	31	8×8	64	SAD	1024×768
[34]	Xilinx Virtex	25.6	5×5	255	SAD	512×512
[28]	Altera Cyclone III	30	5×5	64	SAD	1396×1110
Our work	Altera Cyclone IV	30	3×3	20	SAD	640×480

5. CONCLUSION

This work proposes real time hardware architecture for a stereo vision system. The design has been implemented in VHDL, then synthesized and routed in an altera Cyclone IV FPGA. This new architecture is based on parallel data access and processing, and uses a new design of the SAD block to accelerate the massive computation time associated with the disparity map generation of the stereo vision system. The experimental results show that the speed of our complete stereo vision system can process 30 fps with 640×480 resolution for the 20 pixels disparity range architecture. The proposed system can be adopted to support real time applications such as automotive and robot navigation.

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